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Photocatalytic Activity of ZnO Nanopowders: the Role of Production Techniques in the Structure Defects Formation

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The effect of the type of structural defects on the photocatalytic properties of ZnO nanopowders were studied for phenol photodegradation under UV irradiation. It was shown that the use of different types of precursors for the production of ZnO leads to the formation of materials with the same phase composition and energy of the forbidden band, but different photocatalytic activity. The peculiarities of the DRS, luminescence and ESR spectra indicate the formation of different types of defects in the structure of the material: oxygen vacancies in the anionic and zinc vacancies in the cationic sublattices of ZnO synthesized from ZnC_2O_4 and $\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$, respectively.

Introduction

Resource-saving, energy efficiency and clean technologies have been recognized as priority areas of the world economy and have been intensively developing lately. Their effectiveness is determined by the materials used in the manufacture of active functional components for these technologies. Photocatalytic materials are the most interesting for these applications, because they use the energy of the sun to trigger the mechanism of its functioning [1]. However, their functionality depends on several factors: the physical properties of the material (the energy position of band gap and the band gap width, the photon lifetime, etc.) and the chemical properties of the material (the nature of active surface centers, the ability to generate active forms of oxygen).

Recently, several reviews have been published on the photocatalytic activity of zinc oxide in various processes [2]. However, data analysis shows a wide spread of the photocatalytic activity data of the material for similar processes [3]. We think that this fact is the result of the use of materials with different structural defects which depend on methods of obtaining of materials, preparation of catalysts, type of precursors, etc.

Therefore, in order to understanding the effect of structural peculiarities of a material on its photocatalytic activity, the same material with the same chemical and phase composition but with different types of defects will be studied in this paper.

Experimental

ZnO nanoparticles were synthesized using a precipitation technique from ZnCl_2 salt. As a precipitant the water solutions of ammonia hydroxide and oxalic acid were used. All used chemicals were of chemical purity. A precipitate was obtained by the addition of an aqueous solution of ZnCl_2 in NH_4OH water solution or oxalic acid water solution with continuously stirring using a propeller stirrer for 30 min. The value of the pH was more than 8. The precipitates were recovered by suction filtration using a vacuum pump. The sediments were washed several times with distilled water before drying in a microwave furnace ($P = 700 \text{ W}$, $f = 2.45 \text{ GHz}$). The dried precipitates were calcined in a resistive furnace at 500 and 700°C with a dwell time of 2 h.

The powders were characterized by means of X-ray diffraction (Dron-3) with $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation for crystallite sizes and quantitative phase analyses. Particle sizes of different calcined powders were estimated by means of transmission electron microscopy (JEM 200, Jeol, Japan).

The optical properties of ZnO nanopowders were measured on a Cary 5000 UV-Vis-NIR spectrometer with Internal Diffuse Reflectance sphere (Agilent Technologies, USA). The electron spin resonance (ESR) investigation was carried out on ESR spectrometer CMS-8400 (Adani, Belarus) at room temperature. A charge-carrier dynamics in synthesized ZnO particles was determined by the time resolved microwave conductivity (TRMC) method [4].

Luminescence spectra of different kinds of zinc oxide were obtained using LUMINA fluorescence spectrometer (Thermo Scientific, USA). Decay curves were measured by the TimeHarp 260 NANO system and the single photon detector PMA 182 (PicoQuant, Germany). An excitation of luminescence was induced by the third harmonic (355 nm) of the Nd:YAG pulsed laser (NL202 model, EKSPLA, Lithuania).

The photocatalytic activity of the ZnO particles was tested by photodegradation of phenol used as model pollutant in water with concentration of 50 ppm under UV illumination. The photodegradation tests were carried out in 400 ml water cooled reactor containing 350 mL of the phenol solution and 0.9 g/L of photocatalyst. The photocatalytic tests were conducted under oxygen bubbling at a fixed rate flow. Aliquots of 10 mL were sampled from the reactor at different time intervals. The powder was separated by filtration and then the resultant transparent solution was analyzed by High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC, Agilent 1260) equipped with a UV-detector set at 260 nm for phenol analysis.

Results and discussion

Figure 1 shows the TEM images of zinc oxide nanoparticles synthesized by chemical precipitation from different precursors: zinc oxalate (Fig 1a, c) and zinc hydroxide (Fig. 1b, d) and fired at different temperatures 500°C and 700°C.

Fig.1 TEM images of zinc oxide nanoparticles synthesized by chemical precipitation from: zinc oxalate – a, c) and zinc hydroxide – b, d) and fired at 500°C – a, b) and 700°C – c, d).

According to XRD data zinc oxide crystallized in the wurtzite structure P63mc, regardless of the type of precursor used for synthesis. XRD data shows that the coherent scattering area of ZnO synthesized from zinc oxalate was 32 nm and 47 nm after calcination at a 500 and 700°C, respectively, and for ZnO synthesized from zinc hydroxide was 47 nm and 48 nm after calcination at a 500 and 700°C, respectively. A comparison of the XRD and TEM data shows that the use of the zinc hydroxide as a precursor leads to formation of highly aggregated zinc oxide particles, especially at low calcination temperatures.

The data of UV-Vis diffuse reflectance spectra for zinc oxide synthesized from different precursors shown that the edge of adsorption band for zinc oxide prepared from zinc oxalate is 385 nm (EB = 3.2 eV) and the edge of adsorption band for zinc oxide prepared from zinc hydroxide is 397 nm (EB = 3.12 eV).

The luminescence spectra of zinc oxide powders obtained by different technologies are shown in Figure 2. The excitation wavelength is 360 nm.

Fig. 2 Luminescence spectra of the zinc oxide nanopowders synthesized from different precursors at $\lambda_{ex} = 360$ nm: a) zinc oxalate, b) zinc hydroxide and calcined at 500 and 700 °C.

It was shown that the luminescence spectra of zinc oxide powders synthesized from oxalate hydroxide precursors are different. In the luminescence spectrum of a ZnO nanopowder synthesized from zinc oxalate a green luminescence band ($\lambda = 510$ nm) was observed, while a red luminescence band ($\lambda = 650$ nm) was found in the luminescence spectrum of a ZnO nanopowder synthesized from zinc hydroxide precursor.

The detailed analysis of luminescence

spectra indicates about presence in the structure of zinc oxide synthesized from different precursors own defects of various types. The nonradiative transition of a free electron from the conductive band to the level of oxygen vacancy and the radiative transition from the level of the oxygen vacancy (V_o) to the valence band can be one of the mechanisms of the appearance of the green luminescence band in zinc oxide. Whereas, an additional appearance of zinc vacancies (V_{Zn}) in the system leads to the donor-acceptor mechanism of luminescence (V_o - V_{Zn}) and leads to the appearance the yellow-orange and red bands in the luminescence spectrum. These thesis also confirmed by TRMC data.

ESR spectra of zinc oxide nanoparticles synthesized from zinc oxalate precursor and calcined at different temperatures did not contain any signals (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 ESR signals of ZnO powders, synthesized from different precursors and calcined at different temperatures. Reference peaks Mn(II) in cubic MgO is shown.

At the same time the ESR spectrum generated of zinc oxide nanopowder prepared from zinc hydroxide and calcined at 500°C demonstrate the signal with $g=2.0024$. According to literature analysis the signal with such g -factor are

Keywords: zinc oxide, defects, oxygen vacancies, cation vacancies, photocatalytic activity

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correspond to the charged Zn vacancies (V_{Zn}^-) or V_{Zn}^- - Zn_i complex [5].

On Figure 4 the normalized concentration of phenol (C/C_0) versus illumination times was shown.

Fig. 4 Photocatalytic degradation of phenol in presence of ZnO nanoparticles synthesized from different precursors.

It has been found that the ZnO prepared from zinc oxalate precursor shows the higher photocatalytic activity than ZnO synthesized from zinc hydroxide precursor. As we noted above these systems have different kinds of surface defects – V_o for first case and V_{Zn} for second case.

Conclusions

The difference in the photocatalytic properties of zinc oxide synthesized from different precursors can be attributed to the different nature of defects in zinc oxide formed in these synthetic approaches. It was shown that zinc oxide with oxygen vacancies is more effective as a photocatalyst for phenol degradation. The decrease in the photocatalytic activity of Zn-depleted oxide (V_{Zn}) is due to both factors: a less efficient charge separation and a decrease in the concentration of reactive oxygen species involved in the phenol degradation reaction.